

The Structure of *Salmalia Malabarica* Gum.* Part II. Structure of the Degraded Gum

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Hydrolysis of the methylated degraded gum affords 2,4,6- and 2,3,4-tri-, 2,6-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactoses and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galacturonic acid in equivalent amounts. The degraded gum is concluded to be a branched chain polysaccharide and the repeating unit consists of a framework of D-galactopyranose residues with main chain linked 1→3 and with side chains attached by 1→4 linkages. Periodic acid oxidation experiments also confirm this view

An earlier investigation¹ of *Salmalia malabarica* gum has shown that the gum is composed of residues of L-arabinose, D-galactose, D-galacturonic acid, and a trace of another sugar, probably rhamnose. The ratio of galactose and arabinose in the gum is estimated to be 2:1. On partial acid hydrolysis, the gum furnishes an aldobiuronic acid, 6-*O*-β-D-galacturonic acid-D-galactose along with D-galactose and L-arabinose. Controlled acid hydrolysis of the gum yields a degraded gum, the structure of which has been proposed from the results of methylation and periodic acid oxidation experiments.

A sample of the degraded gum (arabinose-free; equiv., 630), prepared by hydrolysis of *Salmalia malabarica* gum with 0.01*N* sulphuric acid, was converted into its fully methylated derivative (OMe, 41.8%). Methanolysis and subsequent acid hydrolysis of the methylated polysaccharide furnished acidic and neutral sugar fractions. The acid component was characterised as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galacturonic acid through its crystalline amide, m.p. 152°. The neutral sugar fraction on chromatographic separation was found to consist of 2,4,6-tri-, 2,3,4-tri-, and 2,6-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactoses together with a very small amount of 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose. The identity of all the di- and tri-*O*-methyl sugars was established from measurement of their optical rotations and m.p.s of their characteristic crystalline aniline derivatives. The tri-*O*-methyl-D-galacturonic acid, 2,4,6-tri-, 2,3,4-tri-, and 2,6-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactoses were found to be present in the molar ratio of 1:1:1:1. Isolation of the four cleavage fragments from the methylated degraded gum indicates its branched chain character and also demonstrates that all the D-galactose and D-galacturonic acid residues are of pyranose structure and these are joined either by 1→3 or 1→6 linkages. A number of possible structures for the repeating unit of the degraded *Salmalia malabarica* gum could be suggested to accommodate the experimental results, but the final selection (II) is made after considering the structure of aldobiuronic acid, 6-*O*-β-D-galacturonic acid-D-galactose (I), isolated earlier¹ from the gum. It appears therefore that the average repeating unit (II) occurring in the degraded gum carries a main chain of 1→3 linked D-galactopyranose and the aldobiuronic acid is attached as a side chain to the galactan backbone.

*N.S.I. Communication No. 15 on the structure of plant polysaccharides.

1. Bose and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 257.

[GalP = galactopyranose; Gal PA = galacturonic acid].

Isolation of an equivalent amount of 2,6-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose as a hydrolysis product of the methylated degraded gum indicates that this galactose unit is the point of branching and the aldobiuronic acid residue is attached to the position-4 of this moiety. The structure (II) for the average repeating unit is also in agreement with the equivalent weight of the degraded gum. The absence of tetramethyl sugars in the methanolysis product indicates that in the degraded gum, probably, the branching starts from the non-reducing end of the main chain and consequently (III) can be suggested as one of the possible structures for the degraded gum which accommodates all the known types of linkages present. It is not yet known if the minor product of hydrolysis of the methylated degraded gum, namely, 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose, is of any structural significance.

Further confirmation of the mode of union of sugar units in the major part of the degraded *Salmalia malabarica* gum (III) is forthcoming from the results of the periodate oxidation studies. Oxidation of the degraded gum with sodium metaperiodate is found to produce 2.3 moles of formic acid per equivalent with concomitant consumption of 4.3 moles of periodate. The periodate-oxidised gum consisting mainly of 1-3 linked D-galactopyranose residues furnished on hydrolysis 1.8 moles of D-galactose per equivalent. This finding eliminates the possibility of 1-6 linkage in the main chain of the degraded gum. It may be observed that the arrangement of different sugar units in the degraded *Salmalia malabarica* gum resembles closely that of the degraded arabic acid² with the difference

that in the former the aldobiuronic acid branching starts from the non-reducing end of the main chain, whereas it is not so in the latter case.

EXPERIMENTAL

Paper chromatographic analysis was carried out in the same way as reported earlier¹. *p*-Anisidine phosphate was used as a spray reagent. The specific rotations reported are equilibrium values and the melting points are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out at 40-50° under reduced pressure and the methylations were done in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Aniline derivatives of methylated sugars were prepared by refluxing the sugar in ethanolic aniline for 2 hours.

Isolation of the Barium Salt of the Degraded Gum.—Purified *Salmalia malabarica* gum (70 g.) was hydrolysed with 0.01*N*-H₂SO₄ (1 litre) on a boiling water bath for 120 hours. The resulting solution was neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered, and the filtrate after concentration to a small volume was poured into excess of methanol. The precipitated barium salt of the degraded gum was filtered, washed well with methanol, and dried in vacuum (yield 25 g.). (Found: Ba, 9.83%; equiv. from %Ba, 630).

Methylation of the Degraded Gum.—The degraded gum was methylated extensively with dimethyl sulphate and NaOH, following the procedure of Brown *et al.*² The degraded gum (20 g.) was dissolved in water (60 ml) and dimethyl sulphate (250 ml) was slowly added. A 30% solution of NaOH (500 ml) was then gradually added suchwise that the operation covered 6 hours. Stirring was further continued for 12 hours and the reaction product was neutralised with H₂SO₄. The precipitated sodium sulphate was filtered and extracted with methanol. The filtrate and the methanolic extract were combined and evaporated to dryness. The residue was again methylated by the same procedure, using the same quantities of the reagents. The reaction product was worked up by the above procedure and extracted with chloroform in a liquid-liquid extractor to remove the neutral methylated sugars. The aqueous solution was then acidified, extracted exhaustively with chloroform, and the extract was concentrated to leave a residue (13.5 g.). This was methylated six times with Purdie's reagent (yield 11.5 g., OMe 41.8%).

Methanolysis of the Fully Methylated Degraded Gum.—The fully methylated degraded gum (5 g.) was refluxed with methanolic HCl (6.5%, 200 ml) for 10 hours, neutralised with silver carbonate, filtered, and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The syrup, thus obtained, was heated to 55° with barium hydroxide (0.3*N*, 100 ml) for 2 hours. Excess of barium hydroxide was removed by passing CO₂. It was then filtered, evaporated to a syrup, and again saponified with barium hydroxide³. The saponified product was worked up in the previous manner and extracted with chloroform in a liquid-liquid extractor. The chloroform extract consisting of methylglycosides of neutral methylated sugars was evaporated to dryness (Fraction A, yield 1.3 g.). The aqueous solution left after chloroform extraction was acidified with sulphuric acid and again extracted with chloroform.

2. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1724.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1761.

The chloroform extract was evaporated to dryness to obtain methylated uronic acid moiety (Fraction B, yield 0.42 g.).

Examination of the Neutral Methylated Sugars (Fraction A).—The neutral methylated sugar mixture (Fraction A) was hydrolysed with *N*-HCl (50 ml). The hydrolysate was neutralised with silver carbonate, filtered, and silver ions removed from the filtrate by passing H_2S . The solution was filtered, the filtrate aerated to remove excess H_2S , and concentrated to a syrup. The syrup was fractionated into four fractions by paper partition chromatography on Whatman No. 3 MM filter paper sheets, using solvent A'. Strips corresponding to individual sugars were eluted with water by Dent's method⁴. The eluted solutions were concentrated separately to provide the following four fractions:

Fraction I.—The syrup (0.034 g.) on paper chromatography (solvent A) gave a single spot; R_f 0.40. It had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 79.6^\circ$ (c, 0.034 g. in 10 ml water). (Found: OMe, 29.6. Calc. for $C_8H_{16}O_6$: OMe, 29.8%). It was identified as 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose by conversion to 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, m.p. 129° (lit.⁵ m.p. 130-31°).

Fraction II.—The syrup (0.381 g., R_f 0.44) had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 84^\circ$ (c, 0.101 g. in 10 ml water). (Found: OMe, 29.4. Calc. for $C_8H_{16}O_6$: OMe, 29.8%). It was identified as 2,6-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose by conversion to 2,6-di-*O*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, m.p. 121° (lit.⁶ m.p. 121-22°).

Fraction III.—The syrup (0.386 g., R_f 0.62) had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 141^\circ \rightarrow +115^\circ$ (c, 0.1 g. in 10 ml water). (Found: OMe, 41.8. Calc. for $C_9H_{18}O_6$: OMe, 41.9%). It was shown to be 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose by conversion to 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, m.p. 164° (lit.⁷ m.p. 165-66°).

Fraction IV.—The syrup (0.394 g., R_f 0.67) had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 115^\circ \rightarrow +95^\circ$ (c, 0.1 g. in 10 ml water). (Found: OMe, 41.6. Calc. for $C_9H_{18}O_6$: OMe, 41.9%). The sugar was characterised as 2,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose by conversion to 2,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-D-galactosylamine, m.p. 176° (lit.⁸ m.p. 179°).

Examination of the Acidic Methylated Sugar (Fraction B)

The acidic fraction after hydrolysis with aqueous hydrochloric acid gave a single spot (R_f 0.65) when paper chromatographically examined with solvent B.¹ It was characterised as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galacturonic acid by preparing its amide⁹. The methylglycoside of the uronic acid was mixed at 0° with ethanol (25 ml), saturated with ammonia, and was kept in the refrigerator for 40 hours. The solution was then heated on a water bath to remove excess of ammonia. On removal of last traces of ammonia and of the solvent under reduced pressure, the product crystallised out in the flask. After crystallisation from ethanol it melted at 152°. (Found: OMe, 49.4. Calc. for methyl-2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl- α -D-galactopyranosiduronamide, $C_{11}H_{20}O_8N$: OMe, 49.8%).

4. *Biochem. J.*, 1947, **41**, 240.

5. Robertson and Lamb, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1321.

6. Dewar and Percival, *ibid.*, 1947, 1622.

7. Abdel-Akher *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, 3637.

8. Hirst and Jones, *ibid.*, 1948, 506.

9. Levene and Kreider, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, **121**, 155.

Periodate Oxidation of the Degraded Gum

Degraded gum (1.92 g.) was dissolved in water (200 ml) and kept with sodium metaperiodate (9 g.) at room temperature for 7 days (18°). A portion of the solution (5 ml) was taken out and ethylene glycol was added in order to decompose excess of sodium metaperiodate. The formic acid produced was determined by titration with 0.1*N*-NaOH solution. The experiment was repeated thrice and the formic acid liberated was estimated to be 1.9, 2.3, 2.6 moles per equivalent of the degraded gum (formula II requires 2 moles/equiv.). Periodate consumed at this stage was 3.8, 4.5, and 4.6 moles per equivalent of the degraded gum (formula II requires 4 moles/equiv.).

Hydrolysis of the Periodate-oxidised Degraded Gum.—The periodate-oxidised solution from the above experiment was dialysed and then hydrolysed in a sealed tube with $N \cdot H_3 \cdot SO_4$. The solution was washed into a beaker containing a known amount of ribose; it was neutralised, filtered, and the filtrate evaporated to a thin syrup. The syrup was resolved into its components by paper chromatography (Solvent A') and the individual sugars, after elution from the paper strips with water, were estimated quantitatively according to the procedure of Hirst and Jones¹⁰. The amount of galactose was found to be 1.8 moles per equivalent of the degraded gum (formula II requires 2 moles/equiv.).

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